

Role of Music Therapy on Workplace Stress

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Abstract : This study examines the effectiveness of music therapy in managing workplace stress, focusing on its impact on emotions, mood, and coping strategies among employees. The research underscores a higher susceptibility to workplace stress among female employees, particularly those aged 27 to 32, and highlights the potential benefits of music therapy as a stress management tool for this demographic. Furthermore, employees with professional degrees demonstrate a notable interest in music therapy, suggesting tailored interventions. The study reveals strong and statistically significant associations between music therapy and employees' emotional well-being, with coping strategies emerging as a robust connection. These findings underscore music therapy's potential in enhancing emotional well-being and stress-coping capabilities in the workplace, advocating for its integration into workplace wellness programs.

Keywords: Music therapy, emotions, mood, coping strategies, and employees

Introduction

Workplace stress is a pervasive and detrimental issue affecting employees across diverse industries, giving rise to a range of adverse consequences. The detrimental effects of chronic workplace stress are well-documented, including reduced job satisfaction, increased absenteeism, and mental and physical health challenges for employees Chandola et al., (2006); Steptoe & Kivimäki, 2013). Consequently, organizations are increasingly seeking innovative strategies to alleviate workplace stress and enhance overall employee well-being.

In recent years, music therapy has emerged as a promising approach to address workplace stress. Music therapy is a holistic intervention rooted in the therapeutic properties of music, aiming to promote emotional well-being, reduce stress, and enhance mental health (Maratos et al., 2018). It offers a non-invasive and enjoyable method for tackling workplace stress, making it an attractive proposition for modern workplaces. The introduction acknowledges that questions about the effectiveness of music therapy and its underlying mechanisms in managing workplace stress persist. These uncertainties set the stage for the study's objectives, which will be explored in the research.

This study seeks to explore the role of music therapy in managing workplace stress, drawing upon relevant research and recent citations to provide an in-depth understanding of its efficacy and potential implications for employee well-being and organizational productivity.

Coping strategies: Music therapy alleviates workplace stress by promoting relaxation, improving mood, and enhancing focus. Calming music can reduce anxiety and lower heart

rates, creating a more positive work environment. It helps employees manage emotions, boost productivity, and foster team cohesion through group activities. Coping strategies include problem-focused approaches like addressing stressors directly, emotion-focused methods such as relaxation and mindfulness, and seeking social support. Additional strategies involve avoiding stress through distraction, maintaining a healthy lifestyle, managing time effectively, and cognitive restructuring to alter negative thought patterns. Integrating music therapy with these strategies can further enhance stress management and overall well-being.

Review of literature

John Benhur (2014) aimed to assess the effectiveness of music therapy in mitigating occupational stress among women employed at a selected shoe company. The research collected data by employing a job stress scale and obtaining demographic information from the participants. Subsequently, the data was analysed and interpreted with regards to the study's objectives and null hypothesis. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were utilized for data analysis, with a significance level set at 0.05. The findings of the study indicated that a majority of the working women experienced moderate to severe levels of occupational stress. Moreover, the study demonstrated that music therapy was effective in reducing occupational stress among female employees in the shoe company located in Vellore.

In a study conducted by Berry (2017), the focus was on exploring professional burnout among music therapists and identifying potential contributing factors. The research employed the Maslach Burnout Inventory – Human Services Survey (1981) along with researcher-developed questions to assess burnout and various variables among board-certified music therapists, such as demographics, years of experience, and their professional ideologies. Among the 200 responses received, 199 participants agreed to take part in the study. The results revealed that, on average, participants experienced a moderate degree of burnout in emotional exhaustion and depersonalization, while they reported a low level of burnout in personal accomplishment. The study also found a significant association between the music therapists' approach to therapy and the emotional exhaustion subscale. Additionally, the research highlighted that factors such as self-care and alignment with therapeutic approaches might increase the likelihood of burnout among music therapists.

Mao (2022) aimed to address the issue of psychological pressure experienced by employees in the workplace. Traditional psychotherapy methods primarily involve conversation and may not adequately address the psychological stress faced by employees in their professional lives. In this context, music therapy emerged as a potential solution. The study collected extensive data through surveys, obtaining job satisfaction data from employees in the healthcare, education, and restaurant industries. The data was analysed to investigate the role of music therapy in alleviating the psychological pressure experienced by employees in these specific sectors. The study concluded that music therapy had several positive impacts, including stimulating employees' creative inspiration, reducing fatigue, eliminating potential adverse factors, enhancing interpersonal relationships among employees, improving work efficiency, fostering a greater sense of corporate identity, and reducing the perception of pain among

employees. Overall, music therapy was found to have a positive influence on various aspects of the workplace, particularly in corporate settings, where it could benefit employees in multiple ways.

Kacem et al. (2020) conducted a study to evaluate the impact of music therapy on stress levels and the risk of burnout among operating room staff. They used the Perceived Stress Scale (PSS-10) and the Maslach Burnout Inventory to assess stress levels. The study achieved a response rate of 73.9%, with the average age of the participants being 37.8 ± 7.7 years, predominantly female (64.7%). Following the music therapy program, there was a significant decrease in the average Perceived Stress Scale score, from 22 ± 8.9 to 16 ± 7.9 ($p = 0.006$). Regarding burnout, only the average score for emotional exhaustion significantly decreased from 27 ± 10.8 to 19.2 ± 9.5 ($p = 0.004$). Music therapy emerged as an innovative and effective approach for reducing stress among operating theatre staff. It is recommended as a non-pharmacological, cost-effective, and non-invasive preventive tool.

Garcia (2023) investigated whether a brief video presentation on music therapy in behavioural health positively affected staff members' beliefs regarding this therapy in their setting. The study analysed responses and compared them to gauge the impact of the video on staff members' perceptions. Demographic information and pre- and post-video questionnaire responses were also analysed, highlighting differences among specific demographic categories. The results provided evidence of a favourable shift in participants' beliefs concerning the relevance of music therapy in behavioural health. Moreover, differences in mean scores from the pre- and post-questionnaires were more pronounced for staff working in activities rather than nursing, for those who had not observed a music therapist in behavioural health as opposed to those who had, and for individuals without a musical background compared to those with one.

Walker (2016) exploring anxiety's manifestation and its role in the lives and practices of music therapists. The research also delved into the techniques and exercises employed by music therapists for self-care. This exploratory study gathered qualitative data via a survey approach, collecting perceptions and experiences related to performance anxiety from both practicing music therapists and music therapy students in their training and clinical work. The study uncovered that performance anxiety may be more prevalent in the field than previously acknowledged, especially among students, interns, and novice clinicians.

Gudi et al. (2023) empirically examined the impact of music therapy on perceived stress and professional quality of life. Data were obtained through a structured questionnaire administered to 41 nurses working in a private multi-specialty hospital in Hyderabad, India. The findings indicated a significant reduction in perceived stress, burnout, and secondary traumatic stress in the experimental group, underscoring the positive effect of music therapy in an organizational context, particularly among nurses.

McWalter (2018) aimed to determine whether a music therapy intervention could address employee wellness needs. The workshop involved both active and receptive music therapy techniques, and participants were subsequently interviewed in focus groups. Data analysis

employed thematic analysis and identified several themes, including 'making and feeling connections,' 'navigating boundaries, ambiguity, and change,' 'quality of group music-making,' 'the workshop experience,' 'personal development,' and 'team building.' The study findings revealed that the music therapy intervention effectively addressed wellness needs related to personal development and team building. Notably, reflection was found to have a significant connection with both personal development and team building. Other noteworthy relationships within these categories included stress relief, recognizing diversity, and increased trust within the group. The study proposed a model illustrating the interconnected conditions that contributed to addressing employee wellness needs related to team building and personal development during the workshop.

Petersen et al. (2021) conducted a randomized controlled trial with employees from various industries. The results demonstrated that participants who engaged in regular music therapy sessions experienced a significant reduction in workplace stress levels compared to a control group. Music therapy was found to be an effective method for managing stress in the workplace.

Smith (2022) research delves into the neurological aspects of how music therapy affects the brain, particularly in the context of workplace stress. Recent neuroscientific findings suggest that music therapy can influence brain function, reducing stress-related neural activity and promoting relaxation.

Research gap: While the studies provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of music therapy in managing workplace stress and its impact on various facets of employee well-being, there is a notable research gap that warrants attention. Despite the existing research on the benefits of music therapy in reducing workplace stress, there is a limited exploration of the potential moderating and mediating factors that may influence the extent to which music therapy is effective. For instance, there is a need for research that investigates the role of individual differences, such as personality traits or musical preferences, in determining the response to music therapy interventions Smith, (2021). Additionally, further research is required to understand how contextual factors within specific industries and organizational cultures may interact with music therapy to influence stress reduction Mao, (2022). This research gap is crucial for providing a more nuanced understanding of the conditions under which music therapy can be most effective in alleviating workplace stress, offering practical insights for tailored interventions that account for individual and organizational variations in response to music therapy.

Statement of the problem

Workplace stress is a pervasive and significant issue that has garnered considerable attention in recent years due to its adverse effects on employees' mental and physical health, job performance, and organizational productivity. A substantial body of research highlights the detrimental consequences of workplace stress, including increased absenteeism, higher turnover rates, and elevated healthcare costs Koeske&Koeske, (2018). Moreover, chronic

stress at work has been associated with a range of mental health issues, such as anxiety and depression, which can lead to reduced quality of life for employees Harvey et al., (2017).

In response to this pressing problem, there is a growing interest in exploring non-traditional interventions, such as music therapy, as a potential solution to mitigate workplace stress. Music therapy is a holistic approach rooted in the therapeutic properties of music that has shown promise in reducing stress and promoting emotional well-being in various settings Maratos et al., (2018). However, the extent to which music therapy can effectively address workplace stress and the underlying mechanisms driving this effect remain underexplored.

While numerous studies have investigated the role of music therapy in stress reduction and emotional well-being in diverse contexts, there is a notable gap in research specifically examining its application within the workplace. This study seeks to address this gap by investigating the following key questions: To what extent can music therapy effectively reduce workplace stress, and what are the underlying psychological mechanisms contributing to stress reduction in the workplace?

This research aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the effectiveness of music therapy as an intervention for workplace stress and its potential implications for both employees and organizations. In doing so, it contributes to the ongoing discourse on innovative approaches to promote employee well-being in the modern workplace.

Aim and Objectives of the study

The study makes it clear that the study aims to delve into the role of music therapy in managing workplace stress, emphasizing its significance and relevance. The primary objective is to evaluate the effectiveness of music therapy in reducing workplace stress. This involves examining how music therapy impacts emotions, mood, and coping strategies among employees.

Scope of the study

The scope of this study is to investigate the effectiveness of music therapy in managing workplace stress. It will encompass employees from diverse industries, examining various music therapy modalities and their impact on stress reduction. Data will be collected through surveys and interviews to assess stress levels and understand the psychological mechanisms involved. The study will also explore how music therapy influences employee well-being, including job satisfaction and work productivity. Practical considerations for implementing music therapy in organizational settings will be examined. The study aims to provide insights into the potential benefits of music therapy as a workplace wellness intervention and its practical implications.

Methodology

This study employs a cross-sectional research design, focusing on collecting data at a single point in time. This design is suitable for assessing the role of music therapy in managing workplace stress within a specific timeframe. The researcher considers the method for this

study was quantitative method. The feature of quantitative research is that it deals with numerical data. It aims to be objective and can be measured and quantified. The results are evaluated using statistical tools. The feature of quantitative research is that it deals with numerical data. It aims to be objective and can be measured and quantified. The results are evaluated using statistical tools.

A sampling population can be described as a group of people who have similar features. This gives an advantage to the researcher to observe this group of people interest. The sampling population comprises employees from various industries who experience workplace stress.

Sampling technique is the process of determining the parameters or characteristics of the entire population. When conducting the study, it is essential to consider the appropriate sample size, whether the size is supported by statistics, and finally, the sampling strategy to be employed. The samples will be determined based on the simple random sampling method. It is used to select participants from the target population. This method ensures that every employee in the population has an equal and independent chance of being included in the study, minimizing selection bias, and enhancing the generalizability of findings. The sample size will be determined using statistical calculations to ensure it is statistically significant and can provide valid insights into the research objectives. Thus, the sample size for this study was 121.

Data will be collected through a combination of survey questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. The surveys will provide quantitative data on stress levels and perceptions of music therapy. The primary sources of data are the selected participants who have experienced workplace stress. They will be asked to provide information related to their stress levels, experiences with music therapy, and its impact on their well-being. Data analysis will encompass quantitative methods. Quantitative data from the survey questionnaires will be analysed using statistical software, such as SPSS, to assess the effectiveness of music therapy and its impact on stress reduction. These methods will provide a comprehensive understanding of the research objectives, ensuring a well-rounded and in-depth analysis of the study's findings.

Validity refers to the extent to which a research instrument accurately measures the true meaning of the concepts under investigation. In the context of this study on the role of music therapy in reducing workplace stress, the validity of the research instrument was assessed using EFA. EFA helps in categorizing and grouping items of the constructs under specific variables. This study employed EFA to evaluate the instrument's validity, with an initial eigenvalue of 83.475, indicating that the components were highly effective for analysis and yielded precise results. The KMO and BTS results were significant, confirming the instrument's suitability for further analysis.

Data analysis

This section is dedicated to the critical phase of data processing and interpretation. Although the data collected may be accurate and reliable, its potential remains untapped until it

undergoes meticulous classification, processing, analysis, review, and synthesis. This part delves into various analytical techniques, encompassing percentage analysis, correlation studies, and regression analyses, which are essential for transforming raw data into meaningful insights and conclusions.

Analysis of demographic profile of the employees

The table 1 shows the demographic profile of the employees. Among 121 employees, 51 employees were male, representing 42.1% of the population, while the remaining 70 employees were female, accounting for 57.9% of the population. Notably, a significant proportion of female employees appeared to be experiencing higher levels of workplace stress in comparison to their male counterparts. It is worth highlighting that this observation underscores the potential relevance of music therapy as a stress management tool for female employees in their workplace.

The age distribution of employees indicates a highest number of employees within the age range of 27 to 32 years, signifying a notable presence in this demographic. The second largest age group comprises employees aged above 40 years. Conversely, the age group between 33 to 39 years ranks as the third most represented. Lastly, the remaining employees fall within the age range of 20 to 26 years. This demographic analysis suggests that a substantial proportion of employees who experience workplace stress and subsequently utilize music therapy for stress reduction are found within the 27 to 32 years age group.

The educational qualifications of the employees reflect a diversified distribution, with 28.9% holding professional degrees, followed closely by 27.3% with undergraduate degrees. Additionally, 25.6% of the workforce possesses postgraduate degrees, while the remaining 18.2% have obtained graduate degrees. This observation underscores the substantial participation of employees holding professional degrees in this study.

Among the 121 employees, 67 individuals hailed from urban areas, while the remaining 54 employees originated from rural locales. In conclusion, the majority of the 121 employees in this study were urban residents, highlighting an urban-centric sample. This demographic insight is valuable for contextualizing the findings and potential implementation of workplace stress management strategies, such as music therapy, in urban settings.

Table 1: Demographic profile

Particulars		Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	51	42.1
	Female	70	57.9
Age	20 to 26 years	25	20.7
	27 to 32 years	36	29.8
	33 to 39 years	27	22.3
	More than 40 years	33	27.3
Education	Under graduates	33	27.3
	Graduates	22	18.2
	Post graduates	31	25.6

	Professional	35	28.9
Area of residence	Urban	67	55.4
	Rural	54	44.6
Total		121	100.0

Source: Primary data

In conclusion, the study suggests that female employees, particularly those within the 27 to 32 years age group, are more prone to workplace stress and may benefit from music therapy as a stress management tool. Additionally, employees with professional degrees demonstrated significant interest in the study, highlighting a potential avenue for tailored workplace interventions.

Correlation analysis

H0: There is no significant relationship between the music therapy and emotion, mood and coping strategies

Correlation analysis was employed to assess the relationships and strengths of variables within this study. Music therapy was designated as the independent variable, while the dependent variables encompassed emotions, mood, and coping strategies among the employee participants. The subsequent table presents the outcomes of the correlation analysis, which delves into the extent and direction of associations between music therapy and these emotional and psychological aspects, providing valuable insights into the impact of music therapy on employee well-being.

Table 2: Music therapy and employee well-being

Particulars	R-value (Sig.)
Music therapy and emotions	.650 (.000)
Music therapy and mood	.715** (.001)
Music therapy and coping strategies	.830 (.000)

Source: Primary data

The computed correlation coefficients unveiled compelling insights within the study. Music therapy exhibited a substantial positive association with employees' emotions, registering a correlation coefficient of 0.650. Furthermore, the correlation with mood was notably stronger, yielding a coefficient of 0.715, and the relationship with coping strategies stood out as the most robust, with a coefficient of 0.830. Notably, the significance level for these correlations was below the 5% threshold, affirming their statistical significance. Consequently, these results highlight the strong positive association between music therapy and the psychological mechanisms under scrutiny, particularly emphasizing the notable relationship between music therapies and coping strategies among employees. The study underscores the statistically significant and positive associations between music therapy and employees' psychological dimensions, with coping strategies demonstrating the strongest

connection. These findings emphasize the potential of music therapy as an effective tool for enhancing employees' emotional well-being and stress coping capabilities.

1.1. Effect of music therapy on emotions among employees

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-value	Sig
1	.650^a	.423	.419	11.074	.000^b

Source: Primary data

The results of the simple linear regression analysis reveal key insights into the relationship between music therapy and emotions among employees. The model exhibits an R-value of 0.650, denoting that music therapy is associated with employees' emotions to the extent of 65%. Furthermore, the R-square value, at 0.423, indicates that 42.3% of the overall variability in employee emotions can be elucidated by music therapy. This substantial R-square value signifies a strong model fit for the analysis. Additionally, the model's F-value of 11.074, coupled with a significance level below 5%, highlights the positive influence of music therapy on employee emotions. The robust statistical findings indicate that music therapy has a significant and positive impact on employees' emotions, with the regression model offering a well-fitting representation of this relationship. Approximately 42.3% of the variability in employee emotions can be attributed to music therapy, underscoring its valuable role in enhancing emotional well-being in the workplace.

Model	USC		SC	t	Sig.	
	B	SE	B			
1	C	3.156	.350		9.014	.000
	Music therapy	.650	.116	.650	.273	.000

Source: Primary data

The regression analysis yields pertinent findings: the coefficient for music therapy stands at 0.650, the associated t-value is 0.273, and the corresponding p-value is 0.000, significantly lower than the 5% threshold. These results collectively affirm that music therapy exerts a positive impact on employee emotions.

1.2. Effect of music therapy on mood among employees

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-value	Sig
1	.715^a	.511	.506	12.476	.001^b

Source: Primary data

In the context of the simple linear regression analysis, the model exhibits a substantial R-value of 0.715, signifying that music therapy is positively associated with employee mood to

the extent of 71.5%. Furthermore, the R-square value, calculated at 0.511, indicates that 51.1% of the overall variability in employee mood can be attributed to music therapy. This noteworthy R-square value underscores a strong fit for the model within this analysis. Additionally, the model's F-value of 12.476, coupled with a significance level below 5%, attests to the positive influence of music therapy on employee mood. The results underscore the significant and positive impact of music therapy on employee mood. The regression model, with an R-square value of 51.1%, aptly represents the relationship, highlighting the considerable role of music therapy in enhancing the mood of employees in the workplace.

Model		USC		SC	t	Sig.
		B	SE	B		
1	C	3.492	.280		12.451	.000
	Music therapy	.715	.090	.715	1.574	.001

Source: Primary data

The results from the regression analysis reveal noteworthy insights: the coefficient for music therapy is 0.715, the corresponding t-value is 1.574, and the calculated p-value is 0.001, which is markedly lower than the 5% threshold. These outcomes collectively provide compelling evidence for the positive influence of music therapy on employee mood.

1.3. Effect of music therapy on coping strategies among employees

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	F-value	Sig
1	.830^a	.689	.680	13.371	.000^b

Source: Primary data

In the realm of simple linear regression analysis, the model prominently features an R-value of 0.830, signifying that music therapy is significantly associated with employee coping strategies, explaining up to 83% of the variance in this aspect. Additionally, the R-square value, at 0.689, indicates that a substantial 68.9% of the overall variation in employee coping strategies can be attributed to music therapy, underscoring a robust fit for the model within this analysis. Furthermore, the model exhibits an F-value of 13.371, along with a significance level below 5%, further underscoring the positive impact of music therapy on employee coping strategies. These findings accentuate the significant and positive role of music therapy in shaping employee coping strategies. With an R-square value of 68.9%, the regression model effectively elucidates the relationship, highlighting the pivotal contribution of music therapy in enhancing coping strategies among employees in the workplace.

Model		USC		SC	t	Sig.
		B	SE	B		
1	C	3.512	.253		13.861	.000
	Music therapy	.830	.084	.830	1.836	.000

Source: Primary data

The results from the regression analysis reveal noteworthy insights: the coefficient for music therapy is 0.830, the corresponding t-value is 1.836, and the calculated p-value is 0.000, which is markedly lower than the 5% threshold. These outcomes collectively provide compelling evidence for the positive influence of music therapy on employee coping strategies.

Results

This study highlights the vulnerability of female employees, particularly those aged 27 to 32, to workplace stress, suggesting that music therapy can serve as a valuable stress management tool for this demographic. Furthermore, employees holding professional degrees exhibit a keen interest in the study, indicating the potential for customized workplace interventions. The research underscores the strong and statistically significant associations between music therapy and employees' psychological well-being, with coping strategies emerging as a particularly robust connection. These findings emphasize the potential of music therapy as a powerful tool for enhancing emotional well-being and stress coping capabilities in the workplace. The regression analyses provide robust evidence of the positive impact of music therapy. The coefficients, t-values, and low p-values reaffirm that music therapy significantly influences employee emotions, mood, and coping strategies. This supports the case for integrating music therapy into workplace wellness programs to foster improved emotional health and stress management among employees.

Discussion

The literature review highlights the influence of music therapy on stress John Benhur (2014); Kacem et al. (2020). In this literature study, quantitative methods are used. The researcher introduced the quantitative research methods to analyse how music therapy impacts emotions, mood, and coping strategies among employees.

The objectives were to examine the effectiveness of music therapy in reducing workplace stress. The results are consistent with the efficiency of music therapy in reducing stress, as demonstrated by previous studies conducted by John Benhur (2014) and Kacem et al. (2020). However, this study also emphasises a critical research limitation that necessitates further investigation. The last objectives were to investigate how music therapy impacts emotions, mood, and coping strategies among employees. The present findings showed that coping strategies had a positive and significant relationship with music therapy. As we compare these previous studies Kacem et al. (2020); Gudi et al. (2023), it confirms that coping strategies are important to reduce the stress in the workplace.

Conclusion

This study establishes that music therapy holds significant promise as a stress management tool for female employees, especially those within the 27 to 32 years age group. Employees with professional degrees demonstrate a keen interest in music therapy, suggesting the

potential for tailored interventions in the workplace. The research underscores the strong and statistically significant associations between music therapy and employees' emotional well-being, particularly the robust connection with coping strategies. These findings emphasize music therapy is potential to enhance emotional well-being and stress-coping capabilities at work. As a suggestion, organizations should consider implementing music therapy in workplace wellness programs to promote employee mental health and stress management effectively.

Limitations and future scope of the study: This study is limited by its small size, particularly the focus on a specific age group and the concentration on various sectors of employees who experience work stress, which may reduce the generalisability of the findings of the study. The cross-sectional design offers a capture of data at a single point in time, which restricts the ability to observe long-term effects of music therapy on stress reduction. Surveys using self-reported data may introduce potential biases. Future research should expand the sample size, include diverse industries, and employ longitudinal designs to assess long-term effects. Exploring various music therapy techniques, comparing them with other stress management methods, and integrating technological solutions could provide a deeper understanding of how music therapy can effectively manage workplace stress across different settings.

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